

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Connecting EC2U Innovation Lighthouses - part 2: staff exchange

Report

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I. Introduction

A. Rationale

The capacity for innovation is a prerequisite for progress. Each city and university within the EC2U community has developed its own innovation support instruments. The objective of RI4C2 Deliverable D5.3 was to bring together these stakeholders from the EC2U innovation sphere to form a sustainable network, enabling knowledge exchange within the EC2U community, and, thus, extending and diversifying the EC2U Ecosystem.

The structured approach of the RI4C2 project, which guides the transition from networking to structured networking, cooperation, and finally collaboration, has proven useful. This scheme clarifies objectives and expectations for each phase, preventing overwhelming or overburdening stakeholders with meetings and formats.

- **Networking and Structured Networking:** Establishing connections and sharing basic information through online networking events and workshops, on-site meetings, the list of all Lighthouses of Innovation profiles on the EC2U website or the LinkedIn group were vital steps. These activities helped participants become acquainted and start exchanging ideas and best practices. This foundational step was a prerequisite for all subsequent stages.
- **Cooperation:** Engaging in joint activities like a joint publication or a joint lecture series enhances knowledge sharing. The publication "Recipes of Innovation" showcases successful strategies and methodologies to foster innovation. The "Virtual Lecture Series Innovation" offers different scientific views on innovation by different researchers and practitioners. Long-term availability of both formats has been ensured.
- **Collaboration:** Integrating efforts and co-creating solutions through the Makeathon format has been highly effective in engaging students with real-world challenges. These hands-on events enabled students and citizens to apply their knowledge and creativity in collaborative teamwork on-site and online work to foster social impact.

Figure 1: Left: Integration-activity chart, picturing the development towards a Pan-European Ecosystem. Right: The proposed value of participating in the "Lighthouses of Innovation" network.

B. Previous activities

The activities of D5.3/5.5 were planned according to the overall RI4C2 approach for the formation of an EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE) (figure 1): This deliverable builds on several other activities of WP5 "Innovation Sphere", where the Lighthouses were involved:

D5.3 Connecting EC2U Innovation Lighthouses (part 1)

- Definition of Lighthouses of Innovation
- Outreach to local Lighthouses and survey
- Networking meetings on 9 and 16 May, 2022
- Increase the Lighthouses' visibility with the publication of their profiles in a reader and on the website

D5.5 and D5.6 Recipes of Innovation (part 1 and 2)

- Workshops with the representatives of the Lighthouses to prepare the Recipes of Innovation on 20 and 27 June, 2022 (D5.5)

- “Recipes of Innovation” as a collection from across the RI4C2 ecosystem, including recipes from some of the Lighthouses (D5.6)

D5.7 Makeathon

- The EC2U Makeathon took place on 6-7 May 2024. It was composed of seven individual event tracks across Europe: Coimbra, Iasi, Jena, Pavia, Poitiers, Turku and the virtual track.
- Individual Lighthouses participated as challenge-givers, partners, mentors and judges. For example, the Lichtwerkstatt Jena offered a virtual preparatory training session on Prototyping open to Makeathon participants from all locations, the Polo Tecnologico Pavia offered the working space for the Makeathon in Pavia, and the Fondation Poitiers Université acted as challenge-giver.

Figure 2: The Recipes of Innovation, showing “Pint of Innovation”, contributed by the Lighthouse SPVR (Poitiers)

Figure 3: The Lighthouses of Innovation exchanging dynamically in virtual networking subgroups.

Figure 4: Impression from the Makeathon and an exemplary solution developed answering a challenge proposed by the the Lighthouse Fondation Poitiers Université

II. Offered opportunities for mobilities

A. Invitations and opportunities offered

Throughout the Lighthouses activities, Lighthouses mobility opportunities were mentioned. During the networking meetings and bilateral meetings, the Lighthouses were invited to reach out to the board members and to declare interest in bilateral contact with a specific other lighthouse, with the facilitation of the WP5 team.

B. Staff exchange at Entrepreneurial Week Jena

29 May 2023, during the EC2U Entrepreneurial Week Jena

Hosting Lighthouses:

- Oliver Pänke, Head of K1 Startup Service, University of Jena
- Ede Möser, Programme Manager, International Startup Campus, University of Jena

Guests:

- Patrícia Rita, Entrepreneurship Manager, UC Business Technology Transfer Office, University of Coimbra
- Kirsi Peura, Entrepreneurship Programme Manager, University of Turku
- Jari Ala-Ruona, Entrepreneur in Residence and Researcher, University of Turku
- Sorin Anton, Professor on Entrepreneurial Finance, University of Iasi
- Sebastian Händschke, Head of Digital Innovation Hub Photonics Jena
- Immo Feine, Innovation Manager at Nucleus Transfer Project, University of Jena
- Eleonore Rodefeld, RI4C2 WP5 Team

Agenda:

- Tour de Table
- Presentation of the transfer and start-up support activities at the University of Jena by Oliver Pänke
- Presentation of the strategic entrepreneurship activities at the University of Turku by Kirsi Peura
- Open discussion: How to get recognised and consolidated as a transfer service?
- Joint lunch

Figure 5: Presentations and open exchange during the staff exchange in Jena

Figure 6: The guiding questions, prepared by the hosting start-up service of the University of Jena

C. Visit of UC Business

On 19 April 2023 15:30-17 :00, after the RI4C2 mid-term meeting in Coimbra

Hosts:

- Patrícia Rita und Luís Silva, UC Business Technology Transfer Office, University of Coimbra

Guests:

- Matthias Piontek, K1 Startup Service, University of Jena
- Ricardo Costa, Innovation Lab, University of Salamanca
- Dana Strauß and Eleonore Roderfeld, RI4C2 WP5 Team

Agenda:

- Office tour of UC Business and partnering projects
- Tour de table
- Presentation about UC Business by Patrícia Rita und Luís Silva, UC Business
- Open discussion

Figure 7: Office tour at UC Business

D. Activators Pavia visiting other Lighthouses in Coimbra

From 31st of July to 2nd of August 2024

Hosts:

- Ana Rita Querido and José Miguel Nunes, Student Hub University of Coimbra
- Jorge Figueira, [R&D International Networks](#), University of Coimbra
- Luís Andrade, UC Business, University of Coimbra
- Carla Duarte, IPN Incubator, University of Coimbra

Guest:

- Salvatore Trotta, Activators Pavia

Agenda:

- Visit to the Student Hub
- Visit to the R&D International Networks
- Visit to the UC Business
- Visit to the IPN Incubator

The programme has been designed to present the wide variety of structures and services put in place by the University of Coimbra to foster innovation and entrepreneurship, particularly targeting the student community. Salvo Trotta from Activators Pavia is a founding member of a local association working in Pavia precisely on student and young people entrepreneurial skills, organising events and providing training and networking opportunities.

Each of the visits carried out during the mobility was therefore the occasion to explore the organisation, services and best practices of the hosting structures, to discuss common challenges encountered and solutions adopted.

Salvatore Trotta stated:

“The mobility in Coimbra was extremely productive and enriching. I was able to see up close how the University of Coimbra supports innovation and research, as well as the opportunities offered to entrepreneurs, young innovators, students in general through its various facilities and structures. Also, the EC2U project is an extremely

valuable initiative, as it promotes international cooperation and offers students the opportunity to grow both academically and culturally."

Figure 8: Salvatore Trotta, from Activators Pavia, meeting R&D International Networks, UC Business, and the Student Hub at the University of Coimbra.

E. Lighthouses of Innovation meeting in Poitiers

On 11 June 2024 14:00 – 17:00 at the “H.Tag” shared workspace of Neoloji Technopole Grand Poitiers.

Hosts:

- Romain Lefebvre, SPVR, University of Poitiers
- Thierry Ferreira, Fondation Poitiers Université, University of Poitiers
- Sandrine Doyen and Noura Cherine, Neoloji Technopole Grand Poitiers, Poitiers

Guests:

- Pamela Mossmann de Aguiar, Institute of Interdisciplinary Research, University of Coimbra
- Matthias Piontek, K1 Startup Service, University of Jena
- Ricardo Costa, Innovation Lab, University of Salamanca
- Soile Haverinen, Head of Development, University of Turku
- Elida Rosenhech, Department for Research and Project Management, University of Iasi
- Iustinian Gabriel Bejan, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Iași (online)
- Tommaso Mazzocchi, Polo Tecnologico, University of Pavia (online)
- Dana Strauß, Eleonore Roderfeld, RI4C2 WP5 Team
- Anaïs Georges, RI4C2 coordination team

Agenda:

14:00 – 15:00 Opening Session

- Welcome by Noura Cherine (Neoloji), Thierry Ferreira (Fondation Poitiers Université), and Romain Lefebvre (SPVR)
- Presentation of Neoloji and Sirena Start Up by Sandrine Doyen (Neoloji, Sirena Start Up) (online)
- Presentation of the Lighthouses of Innovation activities by Dana Strauß (University of Jena)
- Each Lighthouse introduces themselves and showcases their innovative work

15:00 – 16:00 Visit of H.tag – Neoloji Technopole Grand Poitiers

Explore the startup incubator Neoloji in Poitiers, interact with local partners, and exchange insights on innovation activities and best practices.

- Presentation of a startup hosted by H.Tag: Olivier Dalle, INSPEERE peer-to-peer backup storage system

- Tour of the building

16:00 – 16:30 Coffee Break

16:30 – 16:50 Reflecting on past activities

- The EC2U Alliance
- Networking meetings
- Workshops
- Recipes of Innovation
- Makeathon

16:50 – 17:40 Planning future activities

- How could the network members continue to work together? *Opportunities and ideas to connect further*
- What formats and grant proposals could benefit from the Lighthouses network and the EC2U Alliance?
- How could new Lighthouses be approached and included to the network?
- The planned activities of EC2U WP9 “Innovation Hub” in 2024-2029 - Ricardo Costa, University of Salamanca

17:40 – 18:00 Summary and outlook

The part after the coffee break developed as a more fluid and really open discussion on the importance of collaboration of Lighthouses and other innovation stakeholders on local and pan-European level. Thierry Ferreira and others pointed out that the goal is to build a value-creating and sustainable network through true collaboration and co-creation in action. Instead of just talking and perhaps quickly forming consortia if a call requests it, the institutions need to grow trust, to talk about their KPIs and big goals and to align them across institutions. And then, to go into action and to produce first results and joint successes quite soon, but with long-term

commitment. The Makeathon was a good example of bringing different stakeholders and institutions together around concrete challenges and to understand that all cities have similar challenges and actors, that can learn from each other and develop best practices together. However, to reach the full potential, sustainability and long-term commitment without the dependency on external project funding and timeframes needs to be enhanced.

At the Launch of the PEKE (12th June 2024), the Lighthouses presented the output and vision for their collaboration (D1.8 Official Launch of the PEKE). There, Matthias Piontek as one Lighthouse said:

“[...] Originally, I am just a startup coach, but to see what is going on in Coimbra, to see what is going on here in Poitiers at the Neoloji incubator, it always helped to open my mind. It also helps to coordinate. [...] I can just recommend to take this brochure, the Recipes of Innovation, and go through that with all the great things we are doing at our universities, in our cities. There are examples, and you maybe can adapt them to your own universities, cities, networks at home. And they were the starting point, or not the starting point, they were developed by discussions, by meetings. And what we take out of that is a framework for the future, a framework of trust and knowledge of what we can do, what we will do. [...]

The persons behind the Lighthouses will also talk in the future, and we have plans to do that in the near future, to bring researchers, students and persons from the civil sphere together with ideas, like we did with the great teams of the Makeathon. It was so impressive for me to see as a judge, what kind of great ideas came up there. And we have so many nice things from the past, like the Makeathon, we will see how that evolves over time.”

In addition, Ricardo Costa shortly explained that the Lighthouses will become part of the future EITEN network in the consolidation phase of EC2U as part of the “EC2U Innovation Hub” work package.

A news article about the Lighthouses meeting was published on ec2u.eu.

Figure 9: Presentations and coffee break at the meeting in Poitiers

Figure 10: Group picture after the Lighthouses meeting in Poitiers

Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem Promising future

Outreach
Various stakeholders are brought together

Relatedness
Concrete challenges and good practices

Sustainability
Results are new resources

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Figure 11: Presentation slide of the Lighthouses at the Launch of PEKE

III. Conclusion

The staff exchange was a successful activity that included several opportunities and formats to bring the staff of the so-called “Lighthouses of Innovation” together on-site, exchange good practices, address current challenges, and deepen connections. Looking back, the structured approach, which transitioned from networking to structured networking, cooperation, and collaboration, has provided clarity and prevented stakeholder overload.

The foundational steps of networking and structured networking, including on-site meetings (this deliverable), online events, and leveraging platforms like the EC2U website and LinkedIn group, were crucial for building relationships and exchanging ideas. Joint activities such as publications and lecture series under the cooperation phase enhanced knowledge sharing and ensured the long-term availability of valuable resources. The Makeathon (D5.7), under the collaboration phase, has proven effective in engaging students and citizens with real-world challenges, fostering social impact through hands-on teamwork.

On the positive side, best practices, particularly in awareness-raising and increasing institutional and political visibility, were effectively shared. The general network and cooperation have been strong, especially with the help of virtual ways of meeting up, such as online events, workshops, and leveraging platforms like the EC2U website and LinkedIn group.

However, the mobility aspect of the exchange has not yet reached its full potential. Although the Lighthouses were generally interested in travelling, it was not easy for them to find the time to visit another Lighthouse. There is also a concern about competition for promising start-up teams, which could affect collaboration dynamics.

In summary, while the connection of the Lighthouses of Innovation has made significant progress, there is still room for growth. By fostering proactive engagement and continued use of the structured approach of collaboration, the Lighthouses are encouraged to further engage in specific individual activities and collaborations. Moreover, they are invited to the activities of the new Work Package 9 “Innovation Hub” in the consolidation phase of EC2U. This continued effort will ensure a more connected and collaborative innovation community with the EC2U Alliance and its Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem.

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